

Review Article

Status and outlook of Solar Photovoltaic Energy utilization in Pakistan – A review

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Accepted: 28 April, 2020; **Online:** 03 May, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3780520>

Abstract: To overcome the shortage of energy, Pakistan must develop its own indigenous energy resources, such as hydropower, solar and wind energy. Pakistan is in an area of one of the highest solar streams in the world. This great potential can be exploited to produce electricity, which can be presented to cold communities in the hilly areas of the north, south, and western deserts. Consequently, this paper discusses the situation and prospects for the use of photovoltaic energy in Pakistan. In this energy scenario, the PV energy shares are in the range of a fraction of a percentage compared to total conventional energy supplies. Main emphasis in this study has been given on presentation of data about photovoltaic energy (PV) installations in the country, the on-going activities, development projects, PV planning and accomplishments of public sector PV institutions and organizations. Fortunately, Pakistan is among those regions where sunlight warms the surface throughout the year and therefore has a strong force of generating solar energy.

Keywords: Solar energy, Photovoltaic technology, outlook and status, PV planning and development.

1. Introduction

Contemporary, Pakistan is confronting a severe kind of energy crisis and it has declined the economic growth in the country [1]. Energy crisis refers to the shortage of electricity or other natural resources. These days our country is suffering from the severe energy crisis. These energy crises can be mitigated by producing energy with the use of non-conventional/alternative resources and utilizing it where possible. Most widely used non-conventional energy resources in

the world are solar energy, wind energy, and biomass etc. In our region, alternative resource which is mostly being under consideration practically is photovoltaic solar energy system. Sun is the major source for producing solar energy which is quite simple and floated directly towards the Earth. Photovoltaic solar technologies are used that convert light into electricity. Solar energy is used in all over the world for electricity generation similarly in Pakistan. Energy demand is increasing by more than 9% annually in Pakistan. It is expected that energy demand will increase 8-fold by 2030 and 20-fold by 2050 in Pakistan.

Midtgardet.al [2] took consideration in the climate of Norway and did experiment to know about the performance of three different types of solar panels technologies (monocrystalline, polycrystalline and amorphous silicon PV modules). It was noticed that temperature effect on monocrystalline was moderate as compared to other two PV modules (i.e. polycrystalline and amorphous silicon PV modules) and the average output power as well as the module efficiency of monocrystalline was considered superlative. Mohammed et.al [3] studied the accumulation of dust particles over the surface of 4 Nos. modules of polycrystalline and it resulted that the efficiency of PV system decrease up to 50% like dust, water vapor collecting on the modules are responsible for the wastage of the sunlight through refraction, diffraction, and reflection. Always the rated standard test conditions (global irradiance of 1000 W/m^2 , module temperature of $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and air mass 1.5) based values are provided by the manufacturer for the PV modules.

1.1. Review of Solar irradiance in Pakistan

Pakistan is included among the countries which come near the maximum solar insolation around the globe. Moreover, 5-7 kWh/m²/day is the range of striking of solar radiation upon 95% of the total area of the country. Solar photovoltaic (PV) system is used to produce electricity from this massive solar energy resource potential [4]-[5]. In Pakistan, the rate of average sunshine on horizontal plane per year is around 1700 to 2200 hours and the range of average striking of solar radiation over it is approximately 2000 kWh/m²/year. Also, the range of striking of solar radiation on surfaces with the slope of about 30 degree facing south is measured around 2400 kWh/m² per year [6]. Therefore, the changes occurring in atmosphere must affect the performance of PV modules. Researchers illustrated that the PV modules of different technologies shows specific behavior for a specific climate. Pakistan suffers from a huge electricity deficiency due to a heavy reliance on imported fuels, and this deficiency has become a significant impediment to socio-economic development in the country. For example, a routine

problem is that electricity supply cannot be maintained during peak hours, resulting in frequent power shutdown of 13–14 h in urban areas, and 16–19 h in rural areas. This scenario creates an increase in local fuel prices and limits potentials in the establishment of new industrial zones. Pakistan is endowed with potential renewable energy resources such as wind, solar, hydro, and biomass. These resources have the capacity to be major contributors to future energy production matrix, climate change reduction efforts, and the sustainable energy development of the country. Pakistan relies heavily on imported fossil fuels to meet its energy needs, and since a global hike in oil prices beginning in 2007, the nation has been struggling, and failing, to bring power to its citizens. Pakistan's energy demands outweigh production by between 5000 and 8000 MW — equal to more than 25 percent of the country's total power usage. Pakistan already derives around 30 percent of its energy from hydroelectricity, however other promising renewables, such as solar and wind power, have next to no presence. But the expansion of renewable fuel sources should be a “major national priority,” according to a recent study in the journal (*Energy, Sustainability and Society*). After reviewing the recent literature, the study's authors concluded that the potential to exploit various other forms of renewable energy is high across the whole of Pakistan. Geographically, Pakistan exists in that area of the world where resources of solar radiations are abundant and are most suitable for both Photovoltaic (PV) system and Thermal Solar Power applications. There are certain regions of south i.e. Quetta valley and Central Punjab which receive maximum solar radiation. Annual direct normal annual solar radiation for Photovoltaic (PV) is the range of 7 to 7.5 KWh / m² / day in bulky parts of Baluchistan and the range between 6.5 - 7 KWh/m²/days in the remaining parts of Baluchistan. Correspondingly, the range of normal annual direct solar radiation for photovoltaic, especially for North Sindh and South Punjab is about 5 to 5.5 KWh/m²/days. Similarly, it is about 4.5 to 5 KWh/m²/days in rest of the country.

1.2. *Issues with Solar Energy in Pakistan*

Sun rays need to have certain ingredients; first of all, climate hampers solar energy. Additional alarming factor is dust; solar energy needs a direct path. Any hindrance causes severe effects; similarly, bad pollution delineates the sun rays. Poor solar radiation towards the earth causes poor power generation. Different solar irradiance from sun create poor visibility of havoc, it needs clear sunlight. Accept this; the solar energy usage is not operative for power generation. Pakistan needs to ensure skies are clear, and also no issues with dusty modules. Similarly, it has

no solar radiation deterrence between the dusty module and no solar irradiance. Environmental agencies to play their important role in this regard, consequently, cleaner atmosphere a must be part of the life. Not only have the entire gadget run on the solar energy, the newer appliances must need to come to the market. Above all, electrical supplies need to be solar power environmental friendly. Since, because of the poor solar systems, it burns household equipment in the country.

2. Solar Technology and Categorization

2.1. Solar power

It is the conversion of incident Sun energy into electricity, directly using photovoltaic or indirectly using concentrated solar power. Concentrated solar power (CSP) systems utilize mirrors, lenses and maximum power tracking systems to focus the incident Sun light of large area into a small beam photovoltaic system. It also uses photovoltaic effect to covert Sun light energy into direct electric current using semi conducting materials. Solar power is clean sustainable and environmental friendly.

2.2. Solar Photovoltaic

Photovoltaic (PV) is the conversion of light into electricity using semiconducting materials that exhibit the photovoltaic effect, a phenomenon studied in physics, photochemistry, and electrochemistry. A photovoltaic system employs solar modules, each comprising a number of solar cells, which generate electrical power. PV installations may be ground-mounted, rooftop mounted, wall mounted or floating. The mount may be fixed or use a solar tracker to follow the sun across the sky.

2.3. Photovoltaic systems

A photovoltaic system or solar PV system is a power system designed to supply usable solar power by means of photovoltaic. It consists of an arrangement of several components, including solar panels to absorb and directly convert sunlight into electricity, a solar inverter to change the electric current from DC to AC, as well as mounting, cabling and other electrical accessories. PV systems range from small, roof-top mounted or building-integrated systems with capacities from a few to several tens of kilowatts, to large utility-scale power stations of hundreds of megawatts. Nowadays, most PV systems are grid-connected, while stand-alone systems only account for a small portion of the market.

2.4. Solar thermal

Concentrating solar power plant (CSPP) is one of the best solar technologies to convert Sun incident light into thermal potential to run turbines and generate power in an affordable way. Solar thermal technology helps to mitigate climate change as a well reduce the consumption of fossil fuels resources. As this technology needs high power solar irradiation which can produce enough heat can only work in the areas where most of the time in the year, then sun provide maximum energy and in this area the weather conditions should be feasible I.e. weather should not be cloudy or rainy in most time of the year otherwise in these areas photovoltaic technology will more efficient. A CSP plant has main four sub-systems which collectively work to produce solar energy. Solar thermal technologies are being installed in many developed places such as Spain, Israel, USA and Greece and developing countries like India, Mexico, Egypt and Morocco. These technologies are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Solar technologies landscape

2.5. Global energy potential

The total sun light radiations absorbed by the land masses and oceans is approximately 3, 850, 000 exa joules/year. The conventional resources reserves are counted in unit terawatt/year (TW year) and equally the renewable energy reserves are weighted in unit terawatts TW. The average power of solar irradiation on earth is 174, 000 TW. 86,000 TW which cover land masses given

by global ice free land is approximately 13, 000 MH, so theoretically attained power would be about 23, 000 TW [10]. The total land masses about 23, 000 TW refers to solar power of the earth global. Which demanded the atmospheric losses should be taken into account and amount of solar energy (200 million TWh/ year). For year 2016 worldwide energy consumption from wind power, hydro power, solar power, wave power, geo thermal power, Bio mass, and OTEC were 25 to 70 TW, 3 to 4 TW, 23000 TW, 0.2 to 2 TW, 0.3 to 2 TW, 2 to 6 TW, and 3 to 11TW respectively. Similarly, for fossil fuels such as natural gas, domestic coal, crude oil, and nuclear power were 215 TW, 90 TW, 240 TW, and 90 to 300 TW respectively.

2.6. Solar Energy Potential in Pakistan

Pakistan must have to take advantage of solar energy resources and must have to develop technologies / skillful personnel for the utilization of these abundantly available resources because it is located at an ideal place under the Sun Belt. Therefore, Pakistan is naturally and geographically rich with solar energy resource. The average global radiation falling on a horizontal surface in Pakistan is about 200-250 watt per m^2 in a day with about 1500-3000 sunshine hours in a year [7]. The south-western province of Pakistan namely Baluchistan is rich in solar energy. It has an average daily global insolation of 19-20 MJ / m^2 a day (1.93-2.03 MWh per m^2 in a year) with annual average sunshine duration of 8-8.5 h [8]. Such conditions are ideal for the operation of almost all solar energy applications especially for PV systems. Pakistan has a potential of 2.334 million MW of electricity per year through photovoltaic and solar thermal system. To overcome the prevailing energy crises in the country, the industrialists should venture in this sector. At present, in Pakistan with the help of International Renewable Energy Agency (IREA) China and private sector buildings of solar power plant in Baluchistan, Kashmir, Punjab and Sindh has been developed. The annual average daily mean solar radiation in Pakistan is shown in Figure 2. To design solar energy systems with optimized performance, full knowledge of solar radiation data for a considerably long period is a prerequisite. For developing countries like Pakistan, the need for empirical models to assess the feasibility of using solar energy seems inevitable due to the nonexistence and lack of reliable solar radiation data. Many models for the capital of Pakistan, Islamabad have been presented to appreciate global and distributive solar radiation. It has been found that with the exception of monsoon month, solar energy can be used very efficiently throughout the year. The suggested models can be used for most of the north-

eastern areas of Pakistan, which are similar to Islamabad in terms of climate and availability of solar radiation, but lacking in solar radiation data.

Figure 2 Average mean daily solar radiation in Pakistan, KWH/sq. m

3. Global Status of Solar Photovoltaic

In the last decade, a PV market grows and rapidly proves its improvement and presence at commercial level. The total installed capacity in the world in 2000 was 1.5 gigawatts that was a peak value. On the other hand, the total installed capacity of PV in 2010 was recorded 16.6 GWp. It is a very high rate to encourage the industry to develop and invest in this field. For instance, Germany stated a national target with installing 51 GWp solar energy projects by the year 2020; in 2010 Germany installed 7.4 GWp and the total capacity of the grid connected systems have more capacity than 17 GWp.

Pakistan is a developing country but in worst condition of energy deficiency where many people are hardly living with minimum energy services especially electricity. As it is an industrial country which majorly rely on governmental energy resources were severely affected since 2 decades. Pakistan needs to utilize and develop its natural energy resources which are abundantly available such as hydropower, solar and wind energy. Figure 3 describes the global renewable energy shares in details.

Figure 3 Estimated renewable energy share of global electricity production, end-2018

During 2016, at least 75 GW of solar PV capacity was added worldwide – equivalent to the installation of more than 31,000 solar panels every hour. More solar PV capacity was installed in 2016 (up 48% over 2015) than the cumulative world capacity five years earlier. By year’s end, global solar PV capacity calculated at least 303 GW [9]. Figure 4 shows solar PV capacity by country and region for the year (2006-2016) around the world. Thus, Figure 5 shows the solar PV global capacity additions and the shares of top countries in PV markets in 2018.

Figure 4 Solar PV global capacities, by country and region, 2006-2016

Figure 5 Solar PV global capacity additions, shares of top countries and rest of world, 2018

3.1. *Scope of PV System in Pakistan*

Unfortunately, in Pakistan, the scenario for the generation of electricity into national grid via interconnected transmission network from its prime resources e.g. hydel, thermal is very poor. Political preferences and efforts towards quick methods of generating electricity using fossil fuels (thermal power) and with the help of rental power production companies (IPP's) severely affecting the overall growth of the renewable / conventional energy resources. In these kinds of situations, private sector which is willing to invest in PV system is facing troublesome to produce economical and environment clean energy in the country. In Pakistan, local manufacturing of PV components is very limited and the companies of the private sector which can provide separate low output power modules are less in number. Though, a basic design methodology is finest but in our country technical and trained people of this optimal technology are very rarely available. About 30-35 years ago, government has set up around eighteen PV stations in different parts of the country for small level of electrification in rural areas. The installed capacity of each PV system was nearly about 440kW. But these systems were no longer in operation after a few years of their deployment because no proper arrangement was made for its operation and maintenance [10]. There seen some improvement in the field of alternative energy resources utilization of PV system from the last twenty years. Pakistan Council for Renewable Energy Technologies (PCRET) in collaboration with Alternative Energy Development Board (AEDB) started ensuring development and sustainability of solar PV in

2001-03. But unfortunately, the progress became low in this field due to provision of less financial assistance and technical manpower resources by the government and foreign investors. Two PV systems each of capacity 178 kW were installed separately in the building of Pakistan Engineering Council (PEC) and in the building of Planning Commission (PC) by the grant of Japan aid program at Islamabad in March 2012. These PV systems are installed to introduce new technology of grid-connected solar power generation which has main idea to promote environment clean energy systems. Also, this aid program helps to acquire technical skills on the solar system components and to contribute in the omission of greenhouse effect.

National Electric Power Regularity Authority (NEPRA) has started a program of open Tariff for solar power plants. It has invited many stakeholders to contribute and support national power grid. The first 100 MW PV power stations were installed by the Tebian Electric Apparatus a subsidiary of Xinjiang Sun Oasis at Quaid-e-Azam Solar Park, Bahawalpur. It started operation in May 2015. As the total planned capacity of this power station is 1000 MW so the remaining 900 MW capacity will be installed by the Zonergy under China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) Project. It is authorized; it would have to generate 1000 MW of electricity after its completion by the end of 2016. Similarly, the other very useful proposed solar power stations in Pakistan are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Renewable power generation plans

Station	Capacity (MW)	Status
Jihmpir wind power plant	6 (Plan to extend to 250)	Operational: Pakistan's first
Thatta power plant	150	Proposed (Solar Power Station)
Wind power plant	1000	Proposed (Wind Power Station)
Wind power plant	1000	Proposed (Wind Power Station)
Solar power plant	200	Proposed (Solar Power Station)
Solar power plant	100	Proposed (Solar Power Station)

The World is basically generating electricity by using three types of PV technologies. These technologies have different efficiency at standard testing conditions (STC) but at operating condition, efficiency is not achieved as module rated. It is because of the environmental factors

and climate changes. In Pakistan, generally polycrystalline PV modules are used in buildings and the efficiency comparison of PV technologies is given in Table 2.

Table 2 Outline and comparison of different photovoltaic technologies

Technology	Characteristics
1 st Generation PV (Si-wafer Technology)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monocrystalline silicon • Commercial PV module efficiency is 15 to 19 % at air mass 1.5 • Polycrystalline silicon • Commercial PV module efficiency is 13 to 15 % at air mass 1.5
2 nd Generation PV (Thin-film Technology)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amorphous silicon • Commercial PV module efficiency is 5 to 8 % at air mass 1.5 • Cadmium telluride cells • Commercial PV module efficiency is 8 to 11 % at air mass 1.5
3 rd Generation PV (Multi-junction Technology)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concentrated photovoltaic (CPV) • Commercial PV module efficiency is 25 to 30 % at air mass 1.5 • Organic or polymer (OPV) • Commercial PV module efficiency is 0.5 to 1 % at air mass 1.5

3.2. *Current scenario of PV technology in Pakistan*

The current installed power capacity is about 25,100 MW in Pakistan; the maximum average shortage is about 5,000 MW and 6,000 MW. Electricity demand is rising at a rate of 10% per year, while capacity increase is only growing at 7%. This shows that by 2030, power demand will be greater than 45,000 MW in the country. In 2000-2001, the national energy consumption was 25.26 million TOES, down 0.11% less than the previous year. During the period from the late 1990s to 2004-2005, the country had an extraordinary period of abundance of electricity availability. In many cases during 2011, electricity deficit had exceeded the level of about 5,000 MW. At a stage in May 2011, the lack of electricity was exceeded to 7,000 MW [11]. During 2011, net primary energy supply was 64,727 thousand TOE compared to 64,522 thousand TOEs in 2011, an increase of 0.32% was recorded throughout the study. However, the growth rate of primary net power supply was predicted to an average of 1.8 percent for the last six years. On the other hand, the rate of increase in final energy usage has remained on average 2.9% for the last six years. The national mix of electricity includes hydro (28.4%), thermal (67.82%) and the rest of resources (3.78%). Data available from other government departments showed that the current total generation capacity of electric power is 23,644 MW. In same way, demand for electricity in the country is 19,735 MW in summer and 14,922 MW in winter season which totally insufficient

for the thick population in around the country. Figure 6 shows the proposed scenario of energy mix in Pakistan from (2013-2025).

Figure 6 Scenario of energy mix for Pakistan

The ratio of social acceptability of PV system in Pakistan as compared to its neighboring countries such as China, India and other like Bangladesh, Malaysia is precisely small due to different kind of hurdles over here. No doubt, it is said, that PV system is at its initial stages in Pakistan but we have tremendous potential of solar irradiance in different parts of the country. For example, India has added 1100 MW of power obtained from solar PV system to its energy production and similarly, China was producing about 3.2 GW of power from renewable energy resources in 2011. A list of top ten countries and their solar power capacities is given below in Table 2. Pakistan as developing country is facing some financial problems to enhance its solar PV capacity. The government should have focus on the PV power generation and remove all interruptions among running projects. Sometimes political instability interrupts the government projects due to politicians' personal interests. The politician should have consensus in all energy infrastructure projects in the country. Go for the solar energy, in the USA, solar economy is growing 12 times faster than the rest of the economy. Solar energy is also leading the creation of jobs for the people in the USA. Pakistan can create many new jobs, provide much needed electricity and this would also benefit the environmental emissions. Many countries such as; Iceland, Costa Rica, Uruguay, Paraguay, Albania, Norway and many others are already receiving 100% of their electricity from renewable energy [12]. The Table 3 describes current positions of top 10 countries which are using solar PV technology for the generation of electric power.

Table 3 Current positions of top 10 countries using solar power

Previous Ranking by 2009	Countries	Present Ranking by 2016	Countries	Capacity(MW) (2016)
1 st	Germany	1 st	Germany	17,193
2 nd	Spain	5 th	Spain	3,794
3 rd	Japan	3 rd	Japan	12,300
4 th	USA	6 th	USA	2,528
5 th	Italy	2 nd	Italy	16,361
6 th	Czech	8 th	Czech	2,022
7 th	Belgium	7 th	Belgium	2,115
8 th	China	4 th	China	8,300
9 th	France	10 th	France	1,025
10 th	India	9 th	India	1,685

Currently, 28 projects with a capacity of 9568 MW are under development within the framework of AEDB policies and procedures. These projects are at different stages of their development. The expected deadlines for their commissioning and yearly cumulative capacities of PV modules are described as follows in Table 4.

Table 4 Yearly cumulative capacities of PV modules

Year	Yearly Cumulative Capacity (MW)
2015	100
2016	400
2017	730
2018	1556

It is concluded that these projects are not enough for the country's total demand of electricity. The scope of photovoltaic technology in Pakistan is far below even though; we have many alternative energy resources. There is political instability in the country; so many energy projects

are interrupted in all the provinces. To overcome these difficulties and problems, proper management and political consensus between ministries and departments should be in place.

3.3. *Interest of government of Pakistan towards utilization of solar energy*

The solar energy utilization initiative was taken by the government of Pakistan on May 29, 2013 in Islamabad, where the first-time solar power on grid power plant was inaugurated, with the collaboration of China under the Cool Earth Partnership. Before it, the first major step was taken by the federal minister for water and power Mr. Raja Pervez Ashraf in 2009 to introduce the solar PV energy project. Subsequently 5 years later, at least 7,000 villages were provided with the proper solar energy service to overcome and reduce the energy crisis in Pakistan. Due to this, the government of Pakistan took the interest in using solar PV energy, and allowed the government of Sindh to carry out a research on the feasibility and scope of solar PV energy in different areas of Sindh as well as in entire region of the country. The result of interest by the government policies towards solar PV was very effective because now in Pakistan there are many solar companies working and offering their services in solar power projects. The work is conducted efficiently everywhere for examples Premier Energy and Alpha Renewables (SMC-PVT) Ltd installed many small domestic projects. The government of Pakistan planned to install 50-100 MW solar PV system in 2013 and at least 300 MW in 2014. In May 2015, the capacity was increased up to 1000 MW and in first phase the 100 MW units were started commercially operational at the Quaid-e-Azam solar park (HDIP, 2015) and further extended into phase 2&3.

4. *Policy, Planning and Strategy*

4.1. *Challenges of PV technology in Pakistan*

An attempt was executed to understand what challenges Pakistan is facing to exploit the great potential of solar PV energy. Still, there have been many issues of transparency and integrity in government tenders and energy projects. The private sector is still not capable of providing large-scale design of solar power plants, engineering, installations, and EPC services. Local solar PV production industry is still in the infancy stages in the country. There are no incentives for households from the government to deploy the solar PV system at home and the resorts. There is no funding available for banks at a low mark up to the level of 10%. There are no national policies, neither provincial solar plan under which solar installations should be monitored and adjusted. Moreover, don't have solar PV standards for the solar system right from the import of solar devices in the commissioning of solar devices and proper installations.

Pakistan is facing great institutional weakness and fiscal deficiencies for solar PV development in the country. Government departments have lack of capacity in solar planning and development of innovative strategies for the electricity generation. In favor of long-term planning and development sites in Pakistan's institutions, they need to make strong policies to promote PV technology in the country. Following successful examples of neighboring countries like China, India and Nepal in regarding solar PV technologies. Solar energy technologies in Pakistan have not been exploited for several reasons, such as fear of the high cost of solar energy technologies, lack of motivation and incentives, and insufficient demonstration of efficient use of technologies. Recently, there has been uproar in government circles on the need to use renewable energy technologies to maintain the environment and improve the socio-economic conditions of people living in remote areas but no implementations. In 2005, under the Pakistan vision for 2030, Energy Security Action Plan (2005-2030) was announced to provide secure energy supplies. The plan emphasized the increase in electricity generation capacity, from 19,540 MW of electricity at 162,590 MW by 2030. Energy mix including nuclear, hydropower, and other renewable energy resources was proposed to generate 143,050 MW as additional capacity under a phased program [13]. Current calculated peak demand of the country for (2016-17) is 25,642 MW and is expected to be 34,445 MW in (2019-20) and 1, 16512 MW in the years (2034-35) [14]. Pakistan is blessed with great potential of non-conventional energy resources that can be used for generating electricity long time. Since, from none of the previous policies were specifically highlighted in renewable energy resources, therefore, the government in 2006 declared a devoted energy policy on the development of renewable energy for electricity production. The policy encouraged power generation plants such as small hydro power plants, wind power, solar technologies and biofuels to generate sufficient electric power. To attract investments, exemptions from duties and taxes are allowed for machinery projects in entire country. The IPPs were also allowed to grow local and foreign finances together with equity and dividend sharing policies [15].

4.2. Policies enactment

Policies for Pakistan's energy sector in the energy department are prepared and implemented mainly by the Ministry of Water and Energy with the provision and direction of provincial energy boards. Subsequently, in 1994 the Government has officially focused on formulating electricity and energy policies, however, most of the policies announced so far focus on ready-

made initial energy resources. In the policy formulation process, in general, no such study has been undertaken for integrated energy modeling exercises for balanced policy making. For the meantime, a couple of studies and exercises in energy modeling are found in the literature with no connection to policy formulation. Nevertheless, the outcome of one of these policies or studies has yielded very low due to enactment issues, so Pakistan has not witnessed any significant economic activity, growth or development in various sectors, according to the set goals.

The Alternative Energy Development Board (AEDB) created by the Government of Pakistan acts as the central national body on the subject of Renewable Energy. In 2006, the “Policy for Development of Renewable Energy for Power Generation (Small Hydro, Wind and Solar Technologies) was published and aimed to:

- Increase the deployment of renewable energy technologies in Pakistan
- Provide additional power supplies to help meet increasing national demand
- Introduce investment-friendly incentives, and facilitate renewable energy markets to attract private sector interest in renewable energy projects
- Devise measures to support the private sector in mobilizing, financing and enabling public sector investment in renewable energy projects

4.3. *Barriers to planning and strategies*

Although there is great potential for solar energy in Pakistan, there are some obstacles that need to be overcome to use this technology effectively and efficiently. One of the major obstacles is the high initial cost, as solar power projects take a long time to materialize their monetary benefits. More specifically, these barriers are briefly summarized as follows.

- Unfamiliarity about market prospective.
- Preliminary costs are too high to start a new solar energy project.
- Limited government grants, banks are not willing to give loans for big projects.
- There are always risks associated with solar energy projects in terms of their performance.
- Confusing policies regarding the contribution of private investors.
- Delicate environmental configuration.
- No feed-in tariff scheme.

- High significance to outdated resources of energy and lack of structural regulations for renewable energy [16].
- Additional subsidies are available for fossil fuels as compared to solar energy and other alternative energy resources [17].
- Unpredictable native technology.
- Local production is limited and there is no production facility of solar cells at national level.
- Dependence on foreign technology for key parts and apparatus.
- Unauthentic solar maps to check the intensity of solar radiations.
- Dependence on foreign staffs to install and operate large solar energy projects.
- Limited material about energy efficiency to make operative policies for mobilizing society.
- Limited marketing and business management skills [18].

5. **Conclusion**

Pakistan has obviously, a great potential for using sunlight for the generation of electric power. Because of the higher costs involved, the solar photovoltaic option is only suitable for areas far from the grid, but it too allows considerable savings on fossil fuel consumption and on the other hand will help to improve the living standard of the people in quality environment. It is predicted that with the increase in the use of solar energy technology, the oil import bill would be reduced, which in fact is a major burden on Pakistan's economy. Well-organized and coordinated governmental organizations need to promote solar PV technology through educating the personnel about the benefits associated with them. It's easy to install the PV module on the domestic side is a solution of peasant peoples who have lived in the dark that they can use PV technology for their personal like reading, making foods and household works etc. While good use of funds in the institutions can bring prosperity for the remote rural areas of the country. GOP to coordinate, facilitate and promote solar energy technologies so as to achieve 5% share of power generation through renewable energies by year 2030. The board has been engaged in initiation of pilot projects in alternative energy fields for demonstration of off-grid as well as on-grid transmission through these projects to the end users. In order to, promptly develop renewable energy technologies in the country the board has planned to attract private investors to invest in this field. Due to the expeditious efforts of the board, large investments have been

attracted through international companies. These companies are planning to initiate numerous projects in renewable energy field.

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Acknowledgement

I would like to thank the wonderful Lord for the grace he provided me during this study. And then I would like to express my sincere appreciation to my respected classmates and colleagues in lab for the support, guidance, and freedom they gave me throughout the project and for their careful editing of my article.

Dedication

Thanks GOD.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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